

Ecofeminism and Ecological Preservation in Mamang Dai's Novel *The Black Hill*

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Abstract: Mamang Dai is a powerful literary voice from Arunachal Pradesh with profound connection to the culture, history and landscape of Northeast India. She received the Padma Shri Award 2011 for her contributions to literature and education. In her writings, Mamang Dai portrays nature and the environment as sentient, spiritual and intrinsically linked to the identity of indigenous communities. There is a deep respect for tribal cultures that is harmed by the destructive forces of modernization and colonialism. The ecological consciousness in her works makes her lament the loss of natural landscape due to environmental degradation. She believes that rivers have soul, land is a living being and natural elements are sacred. Her novel 'The Black Hill' published in 2014, received the Sahitya Akademi Award in 2017. Mamang Dai's 'The Black Hill' is a historical novel set in the mid-nineteenth century in the region bordering Assam and Tibet. Nature and Ecology are intertwined with the cultural, spiritual and historical identity of the indigenous communities of Arunachal Pradesh. The novel presents an ecocentric worldview where the natural world is a living entity, not merely a backdrop for human events. Through her narrative Dai advocates for an integrated approach to environmental and feminist issues.

Keywords: Ecofeminism, Ecology, Nature, Northeast India, Mamang Dai, *The Black Hill*

Ecocriticism is the study of literature and environment and its focus is on the relationship between literature and the

environment. It examines how natural themes are represented in texts, while Ecofeminism is a social and philosophical movement that links the oppression of women to the exploitation of the environment. Ecofeminists argue that these phenomena are interconnected and rooted in patriarchal system of dominion. Environmental Humanities is a broader field that studies the relationship between humans and the natural world through the lens of the humanities encompassing ecocriticism, ethics and cultural studies to understand our connection to the environment. Both Ecofeminism and Environmental Humanities are concerned with the human-nature relationship, often sharing critiques of how societies have historically devalued the natural world. Both fields question the prevailing patriarchal and capitalist paradigms that historically place humans above nature treating the earth and the marginalized communities as resources to be exploited.

Ecofeminism can be viewed as a specific and activist-oriented branch within the broader interdisciplinary umbrella of Environmental Humanities that consider the exploitation of women and the exploitation of natural world as the two sides of the same coin, often driven by the same logic of dominion. It combines ecological concerns with feminist viewpoint highlighting the interdependence between environmental degradation and the oppression of women and underprivileged people. Ecofeminism is defined in the Oxford Learners Dictionary as "a philosophical and political theory and movement that combines ecological concerns with feminist ones, reading both as resulting from male domination of society."

Webster's New World Encyclopedia defines it as "a movement or theory that applies feminist principles and ideas to ecological issues".

The word "ecofeminism" was coined by the French writer and activist Françoise d'Eaubonne in her book 'Le Feminisme ou La Mort'(Feminism or Death) published in 1974. She argued that women have a special connection to nature because of their reproductive and caring roles and that the destruction of the natural world by patriarchy is intimately tied to its exploitation of women. Thinkers like Maria Mies, Vandana Shiva and Geeta Gaard

contend that social roles, economic systems and cultural norms-- rather than biology-- have an impact on how women interact with their surroundings. Ecofeminism works on several key assumptions:

- The dualism of man and woman, culture and nature, reason and emotion, are patriarchal and hierarchical where the first term is considered superior.
- Systems of power like racism, colonialism and capitalism are associated with interconnected system of oppression that work in tandem with patriarchy to exploit and dominate marginalized groups like women, people of colour , indigenous population and the natural world.
- Colonialism created the conditions for global capitalism through the forceful expulsion and exploitation of indigenous peoples and their lands. The legacies of power and racial hierarchies continue to create environmental harm.
- Women have created sustainable lifestyles that provide alternatives to Industrial exploitation, particularly in rural and indigenous areas.

Ecofeminists like Dr. Vandana Shiva through her work, "Staying Alive: Women, Ecology and Development ", draws parallels between the exploitation and suffering experienced by both nature and woman and has critically analysed the complex connection between gender inequality, environmental decline and social justice. The traditional notion of power is challenged and a call for more sustainable and balanced relationship among human and nature is emphasized. She examines the position of women in relation to nature -- the forests, the foodchain and water supplies and links the violation of nature with violation and marginalization of women in the Third World. Her work has dealt with third world women whose lives are adversely affected by the forces of corporate globalization and colonialism. The Chipko Movement in India became one of the most environmental activism struggles in the world. Vandana Shiva is one of the women involved in this movement which resisted Industrial forestry and logging in rural India. Chipko means "to embrace" in Hindi. Local women

physically hugged trees to protect them and prevent loggers from cutting them. The Chipko Movement served as an example for the broader ecofeminist movement how local communities and women's groups can effectively mobilize to protect the environment.

From Shiva's perspective, women liberation cannot be achieved without a simultaneous struggle for the preservation and liberation of all life on this planet from the dominant patriarchal/capitalist worldview. Shiva and other ecofeminists are explicitly anti-war and anti-capitalist because both war and capitalism are seen as patriarchal structures. For Shiva there is a connection between the escalation of war, "muscleman culture" and rape and other violence against women. In the words of Mies and Shiva " It is no coincidence that the gruesome game of war-- in which the greater part of the male sex seem to delight-- passes through the same stages as the traditional sexual relationship: conquest, possession, control of a woman or a land, it makes little difference."

Throughout our history nature is portrayed as feminine and women are often thought of as closer to nature than man. Nature's ability to create, grow and reproduce is frequently compared to biological and life-giving capacity of women. Women's psychological connection with birth and childcare have partly led to this close association with nature. The menstrual cycle which is linked to lunar cycles, is also seen as an evidence of women's closeness to natural rhythm. Women interact more closely with nature than men do and the intimacy has been traced from the time immemorial. Women's concern for the natural environment is rooted in their concern for the health and well- being of family and even community. Women are often seen as embodying nurturing qualities like care and strength mirroring nature's role as a provider and protector. Many cultures have traditions of worshipping nature as a divine feminine principle as seen in Hindu practices of revering plants like the tulsi and peepul trees. Many cultures use feminine figures in their mythology to represent nature. For example, the Hindu goddess Sita is seen as the embodiment of nature because she is born from earth and returns to earth.

Mamang Dai is a powerful literary voice from Arunachal Pradesh with profound connection to the culture, history and landscape of Northeast India. She received the Padma Shri Award 2011 for her contributions to literature and education. In her writings, Mamang Dai portrays nature and the environment as sentient, spiritual and intrinsically linked to the identity of indigenous communities. There is a deep respect for tribal cultures that is harmed by the destructive forces of modernization and colonialism. The ecological consciousness in her work makes her lament the loss of natural landscape due to environmental degradation. She believes that rivers have soul, land is a living being and natural elements are sacred. Her novel 'The Black Hill' published in 2014, received the Sahitya Akademi Award in 2017.

Mamang Dai's 'The Black Hill ' is a historical novel set in the mid- nineteenth century in the region bordering Assam and Tibet. Nature and Ecology are intertwined with the cultural, spiritual and historical identity of the indigenous communities of Arunachal Pradesh. The novel presents an ecocentric worldview where the natural world is a living entity, not merely a backdrop for human events. Through her narrative Dai advocates for an integrated approach to environmental and feminist issues. The historical event-- the disappearance of French priest Father Nicolas Krick in the 1850s-- has been used to explore issues of cultural transition, identity and colonial incursion. The novelist emphasises the fact how colonial expansion leads to the physical and cultural displacement of native population creating imbalance in natural surroundings. The indigenous people resist the entry of the foreigners, fearing that the priest's arrival will lead to British Military presence and control over their land. There is struggle for identity due to effects of imperialist dominance that challenges traditional ways of life and beliefs. The narrative functions as an act of literary and political resistance advocating for the preservation of ecological and cultural heritages against the homogenized and exploitative forms of modernism and capitalism.

Mamang Dai portrays a strange connection between the female protagonist, Gimur, the indigenous community's cultural heritages and the natural world of Arunachal Pradesh. Gimur is a

young woman from the Abhor (Adi) tribe. She is bold, fiesty and independent challenging the traditional expectations of women in the mid-nineteenth century tribal society. She makes a decision to elope with Kajinsha who is a man from another community. She is a powerful example of an ecofeminist character who draws strength from her environment. She opposes the systems that marginalize both women and nature. Gimur's connection to the land highlights the dual oppression of women and nature by patriarchal forces. The land is seen as a 'book' that the people read and understand, a source of knowledge and history that predates written records. Her deep , intrinsic connection to the land and the indigenous culture are remarkable from the point of view of ecofeminism. Character like the Mishmi chief Kajinsha also struggles against the colonial forces. The tribes unite when they realize that colonizers are invading their shared territory. Kajinsha is a warrior who fiercely defends his land against foreign entry. He is ultimately executed by the British becoming a symbol of martyrdom for the native cause.

Unlike the male characters who engage in open warfare against colonial forces to protect their land and culture, Gimur's resistance is expressed through subtle yet powerful means. She opposes colonial forces through cultural resistance, loyalty to her community and enduring the tragic consequences of the encroachment on her land. Towards the end when Kajinsha dies, Gimur is left alone to lament upon a land that has succumbed to conflict and loss. Despite the personal tragedies and cultural displacement, she lives the life she was meant to live. Her resilience and strength is indomitable like nature itself that withstands disturbances like storms, fires or human impacts and still maintains its basic structure and function. Through Gimur and other characters the novel highlights the fact how women and marginalized groups play a crucial role in advocating for ecological preservation and lead environmental movements.

For Gimur and her community land is not merely territory or property. It is intrinsically linked to their existence .She finds her identity through her relationship with the mountain and her environment. The thick jungles, barren landscapes and formidable

mountains are not just setting, but an active presence and witness to historical event. The land is integral to the identity of the people. Nature also serves as a reflection of the characters' inner thoughts and emotions. Its shifting moods vary from calm and serene to violent and unpredictable, mirroring the emotional and psychological states of the characters. When Kajinsha is filled with guilt and uncertainty, the landscape reflects his inner turmoil: "The sky darkened and the wind howled through the trees as if the land itself was mourning." (Dai, Mamang, *The Black Hill*, Aleph, 2014). In this novel we also find nature influencing the moral and ethical choices made by the characters. When Kajinsha considers departing from his village in search of a more promising future, he is reminded of his strong bond with the land and the duties associated with it. He was unable to leave the land that had provided him with life as it would mean betraying not just his community but also the earth that had protected him from birth.

Based on the above analysis, the ecofeminist themes weaved in the novel, can be summed up in the following points:

- Critique of patriarchy that devalues both women and nature
- The value of traditional ecological knowledge
- Interconnectedness of women and nature
- Spritual and holistic view of nature
- Rejection of colonial exploitation and modernism
- Interconnected oppression of women and nature
- Connection to the land and culture
- Women as custodians of ecological knowledge
- Critique of Western Dualism

- Dual oppression of women and indigenous communities

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